

Sperm Quality and Occurrence of Multi-Drug Resistant *Escherichia coli* in Seminal Fluid Samples of Patients with Diabetes

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Abstract

Male fertility and sperm quality can be negatively affected by diabetes. In addition, multidrug-resistant bacteria are life-threatening. In the present study, the quality of the sperm and the presence of multi-drug resistant *Escherichia coli* were studied in semen samples collected from informed and consented male patients with diabetes (n=200). For assessing sperm quality, parameters such as motility, progressive motility, non-progressive motility, vitality and morphology were considered apart from seminal fluid quality, fructose and zinc content. By routine laboratory procedures, the *E. coli* isolates from the semen samples were subjected to antibiotic sensitivity test to find out the occurrence of drug resistant *E. coli*. The results revealed that the average percentage of motility, progressive motility, non-progressive motility, vitality, and morphology were 21.93, 39.2, 58.28, 36.77 and 3.23, respectively. Out of 36.2% of *E. coli* occurrence in seminal fluid samples, 20.6% were found to be multi-drug resistant *E. coli* isolates. It is possible for diabetes to negatively impact semen quality, while diabetes-related infections of the urinary tract are a significant health concern for diabetic individuals, which calls for careful management of antibiotics.

Keywords: Antibiotic resistance, *E. coli*, Male infertility, Seminal fluid, Sperm quality.

Introduction

In a poorly controlled diabetes situation, nerves and blood vessels can be damaged, increasing the chances of infection. Despite a persistent obesity prevalence, diabetes mellitus is projected to affect 4.4% of the global population in 2030 (Wild et al., 2004). A recent study reported that there are 573 million adults worldwide with diabetes, and the number is predicted to rise to 643 million by 2030. In 2045, there will be 783 million diabetics (Saeedi et al., 2019). Sexual intercourse uninterrupted and unprotected for 12 months will not permit a man to become pregnant with a fertile woman. Diabetic hyperglycemia overactivates metabolic pathways, leading to an increase in reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and oxidative damage to tissues. According to relevant experimental and clinical studies, oxidative damage to pancreatic cells and endothelial dysfunction are the main causes of ROS generation and oxidative stress in diabetes (Darenskaya et al., 2021).

It has become increasingly obvious that genitourinary tract infections can be caused by several microorganisms, including those that cause sexually transmitted diseases, lower urinary tract symptoms, and male accessory gland infections (Hannachi et al., 2018). Various microorganisms have been detected in semen, including chlamydia, mycoplasma, gonococcus, trichomonas and viruses, with variable effects on the genital tract, as well as on sperm quality. Semen has been

found to contain chlamydia, mycoplasma, gonococcus, trichomonas, and viruses, which can adversely affect sperm quality and the genital tract. In addition, pathogenic bacteria cause the majority of infections (Pellati et al., 2008). Pathogenic microorganisms that cause infections have a virulence factor that makes them resistant to antibiotics. Despite the widespread use of antibiotics, there has never been so much resistance in so many locations, and that resistance in so many organisms is unprecedented and growing (Heidari et al., 2016).

Increasing obesity and physical inactivity, population growth, aging, and urbanization are all contributing to the growth of the diabetes epidemic. Although male factor infertility is thought to have the same prevalence as female factor infertility, research on the relationship between diabetes mellitus and sperm parameters remains incomplete (Pergialiotis et al., 2016). This is true in case of Chennai and surrounding districts. Hence the present study has been carried out aiming to explore the quality of semen and the occurrence of multidrug resistant *E. coli* in seminal fluid collected from informed and consented diabetic patients.

Materials and methods

The present research was informed and consented study, conducted in the Dr.Borus Research Institute, Chennai, where the samples were collected routinely from the patients with male infertility associated with diabetes. In order to obtain consent, 150 patients were informed and were sampled after getting informed consent. The semen samples were collected and processed according to the WHO guidelines (WHO, 2021). Recruitment took place between April 2023 and December 2023. Male partners with diabetes attending the infertility clinic were included. An in-depth physical examination, including estimation of testicular volume, followed by imaging and hormonal testing, if necessary, was used to diagnose such conditions. Fructose and zinc contents of the semen samples were also analyzed adopting WHO methods.

Participants in the study were required to provide a written informed consent. A baseline demographic profile was collected, as well as details about co-morbidities and medical histories. As part of the history, a detailed sexual history was provided, including details on frequency of sexual contact, sexual health concerns, and possible sexually transmitted diseases. Participants were also subjected to a thorough physical examination. Upon collection of the semen sample, it was analysed routinely as well as tested for microbes (Cappuccino and Sherman, 1999; Cheesbrough and McArthur, 1976). The microbiological evaluation included microscopic examination of Gram-stained smear and culture for bacteria (*E. coli*) employing specific culture media such as blood agar and McConkey agar. Using Kirby and Bauer disc diffusion assay with standard antibiotic discs, antibiotic sensitivity of the *E. coli* isolated from seminal fluid of the consented patients with diabetic condition. The obtained data on demography of the patients, semen characteristics and microbiological data were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS computer software.

Results and discussion

The diagnosis and treatment of male infertility depend on the quality of semen and sperm. In a semen analysis, parameters like the volume of the semen, the concentration of sperm, and the motility of the sperm are assessed. There are certain abnormalities in these areas that can

contribute to infertility, such as low sperm counts (oligozoospermia), poor motilities (asthenozoospermia), and abnormal shapes (teratozoospermia). Additionally, factors such as infection or hormonal imbalance can also impact fertility, such as fragmented sperm DNA. In this study, the average range of sperm motility, progressive motility, non-progressive motility, vitality and morphology observed were 21.93, 39.2, 58.28, 36.77 and 3.23% (Figure 1). The average value of fructose in semen samples of 150 informed diabetic patients was 49.92 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$, while it was 5.67 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$ for zinc (Figure 2). Out of a total of 36.2 *E. coli* bacterial isolates from a total of 150 seminal fluid samples, 21 *E. coli* isolates were found to be multi-drug resistant (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Average percentage of sperm characteristics of 150 informed diabetic patients.

Figure 2. Average values of fructose and zinc in the seminal fluid of diabetic patients.

Figure 3. Occurrence of *E. coli* isolates in the seminal fluid of diabetic patients and their antibiotic sensitivity pattern.

When sperm are unable to move, they are unable to reach an egg and be fertilized. One of the effects of diabetes is that it impairs sperm motility, particularly progressive motility. As sperm rely on glucose for energy, diabetes can damage glucose metabolism, affecting sperm motility and energy production. Diabetes can increase the proportion of sperm with abnormal shapes and structures, further impacting their ability to function properly (La Vignera et al., 2012). High blood sugar can lead to increased oxidative stress, which can damage sperm DNA, potentially affecting fertilization and early embryonic development (Agbaje et al., 2007). Diabetes can alter the composition of seminal plasma, the fluid that carries sperm, potentially affecting sperm health and function. It is important to note that the impact of diabetes on sperm parameters can vary, and factors like disease duration, glycemic control, and presence of complications can play a role (La Vignera et al., 2012). Antibiotic-resistant bacteria in seminal fluid can pose a significant threat to male reproductive health and fertility, as well as potentially impacting assisted reproductive technologies (Hannachi et al., 2018). Bacterial infections, including those with antibiotic-resistant strains, are relatively common in semen samples. Studies have shown that these infections can lead to a range of issues, including reduced sperm motility, abnormal morphology, and decreased fertilization rates (Pellati et al., 2008). Bacteria develop resistance through various mechanisms, including the overexpression of efflux pumps, biofilm formation, plasmid-mediated gene transfer, and antibiotic degradation. Antibiotic resistance can compromise the effectiveness of treatment, leading to persistent infections and potentially contributing to male infertility. Specifically, infections with resistant bacteria have been linked to a decline in sperm motility and a reduction in the success of embryo development during ART procedures (Heidari et al., 2016).

Conclusion

Antibiotic-resistant bacteria in seminal fluid is a growing concern, impacting both male fertility and potentially contributing to wider public health issues. While antibiotics are often used in semen extenders and treatment of infections, the increasing resistance of bacteria to these drugs necessitates a closer look at alternative strategies and a more cautious approach to antibiotic use in andrology. The present study showed that the sperm characteristics as well as seminal fluid contents were negatively impacted by bacterial infection. The occurrence of drug resistant *E.coli* reveals that the patients need more careful examination and treatment.

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